

QUINOLINE-8-CARBOXYLIC ACID AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART I.

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Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid has been used as an analytical reagent for the estimation of copper. Copper has been found to be completely precipitated in p_n as low as 1.7%. In neutral solution copper gives a distinct precipitate even at a dilution of 1 in 4,000,000 parts.

It was well known that reagents like anthranilic acid (Funk, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, **91**, 332; 1934, **96**, 385; 1933, **93**, 241), α -quinaldinic acid (Ray and Bose, *ibid.*, 1933, **95**, 400), 8-oxyquinoline (Berg, *ibid.*, 1927, **70**, 341) gave insoluble inner metallic complexes with some metals and thus enable the estimations and separations of metals from each other to be made under specified conditions.

8-Oxyquinoline and α -quinaldinic acids form five membered rings with the metal atoms, whereas quinoline-8-carboxylic acid, like anthranilic acid is found to form a six membered ring complex with the metal atom. Like α -quinaldinic acid this quinoline-8-carboxylic acid was found to give complete precipitation with copper, cadmium as also a red colouration with ferrous iron.

In the literature (Skraup, *Monatsh*, 1900, **2**, 532) copper compound of the reagent was described as hydrated needles. It was found that this copper compound lost all its water at 150°. The metal complex of the acid can be represented as follows:

The copper compound is appreciably soluble in mineral acids, acetic acid and in ammonia.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Quinoline-8-carboxylic Acid.—The acid was obtained by the oxidation of 8-methylquinoline with chromic acid. The base was

prepared according to the method described by Knuppel (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 705). The acid is appreciably soluble in cold water, more so in hot water and alcohol; very soluble in acids and in alkali solutions; m. p. 187° after crystallisation from water.

Salts of Quinoline-8-carboxylic Acid.—Copper, silver and calcium salts of the acid have been described in the literature. The copper salt of the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ forms insoluble, light blue, hydrous needles. The calcium salt $2\text{Ca}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 + \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N}$ is remarkably soluble in water and silver salt $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})$ is very difficultly soluble in water. The reagent has also been found to give a white insoluble cadmium, lead, mercuric and thalous salt and a red colouration with ferrous salts. These are soluble in strong mineral acids.

Copper Salt of Quinoline-8-carboxylic Acid.—The light blue copper salt was prepared by the addition of the sodium salt of the reagent to a solution of sulphate, slightly acidified with a decinormal solution of sulphuric acid. The copper compound was filtered and washed by decantation with cold water at room temperature and then dried at 150°. The salt on analysis gave [Found: Cu, 15.59; N, 6.9. Calc. for $2\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2)_2$: Cu, 15.597; N, 6.87 per cent].

The copper salt was found to be slightly soluble also in hot water, and melts with decomposition at about 288°.

Detection and Estimation of Copper.—In neutral solution copper gives a distinct precipitate even at a dilution of 1 in 4,000,000 parts.

A solution of copper sulphate prepared from electrolytic copper was standardised electrolytically. A measured quantity of this solution was neutralised with dilute ammonia and an excess of decinormal sulphuric acid (2-14 c.c.) was added. The solution was diluted to 150-180 c.c. and then to the cold solutions or to the solution at room temperature was added an excess of sodium salt of the acid (1 g. of quinoline-8-carboxylic acid per 100 c.c. solution) drop by drop with constant stirring, when a light blue precipitate of copper was formed. This was then allowed to settle, filtered through a porcelain gooch crucible and washed with cold water. The copper precipitate must be well washed with water otherwise the results tend to be too high due to the adsorption of electrolytes. The copper salt was then dried at 150° and weighed. The amount of copper was calculated from the formula $(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cu}$. The p_{H} of the filtrate from the copper precipitation was determined in each case by the quinhydrone electrode. The results are given in Table I. In Table II are given results due to the precipitation of copper in presence of free acetic acid and in Table III are

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given results in presence of acetic acid and sodium acetate or excess of sodium salt of the reagent.

TABLE I.

p_H Range over which copper was completely precipitated.

No.	N/10-H ₂ SO ₄ .	Reagent.	Total vol.	Wt. of Cu ppt.	Copper		<i>p_H</i>	Error.
					present.	found.		
1	2 ml	10ml, 180ml.	0'1129 g.	0'01759 g.	0'01760 g.	6'9	+0'000008	
2	2	20 180	0'1128	0'01759	0'01758	7'0	-0'000001	
3	4	17 180	0'1130	0'01759	0'01762	6'3	+0'000028	
4	4	17 180	0'1132	0'01759	0'01765	6'3	+0'000058	
5	6	20 180	0'1134	0'01759	0'01768	3'4	+0'000088	
6	6	20 180	0'1131	0'01759	0'01763	3'4	+0'000038	
7	6	17 180	0'1130	0'01759	0'01762	3'02	+0'000028	
8	6	17 180	0'1128	0'01759	0'01758	3'02	-0'000001	
9	7	17 180	0'1128	0'01759	0'01758	2'78	-0'000001	
10	7	17 180	0'1132	0'01759	0'01765	2'78	+0'000058	
11	2	10 150	0'0614	0'00953	0'00957	3'19	+0'000037	
12	2	10 180	0'0612	0'00953	0'00954	3'32	+0'000006	
13	4	20 150	0'1223	0'01907	0'01906	3'7	-0'000001	
14	4	20 150	0'1224	0'01907	0'01908	3'8	+0'000001	
15	6	30 150	0'1835	0'02860	0'02861	3'13	+0'000005	
16	10	30 150	0'1836	0'02860	0'02863	2'91	+0'000025	
17	14	40 150	0'2446	0'03814	0'03814	2'93	Nil	
18	14	40 150	0'2442	0'03814	0'03807	2'82	-0'000007	

In the presence of free acetic acid it has been found that the copper salt has a solubility in free acetic acid.

TABLE II.

No.	N-Acetic acid.	Reagent.	Total vol.	Wt. of Cu ppt.	Copper		<i>p_H</i>	Error.
					present.	found.		
1	8 ml	10 ml, 150 ml.	0'0593 g.	0'009535 g.	0'00924 g.	3'34	-0'000029	
2	8	10 150	0'0581	0'009535	0'00905	3'34	-0'000478	

TABLE III.

No.	N-Acetic acid.	Reagent.	Total vol.	Wt. of Cu ppt.	Copper present.	Copper found.	p_H	Error.
*1	10 ml.	10 ml.	150 ml.	0.0611 g.	0.00953 g.	0.00952 g.	4.86	-0.000012
*2	10	10	150	0.0610	0.00953	0.00950	4.9	-0.000027
3	8	20	150	0.0614	0.00953	0.00957	3.7	+0.000037
4	10	20	150	0.0615	0.00953	0.00958	3.62	+0.000053
5	12	20	150	0.0612	0.00953	0.00954	3.61	+0.000006

* With 2 g. of sodium acetate.

During the precipitation of copper in the presence of normal acetic acid either a few grams of sodium acetate or a large excess of sodium salt of the reagent must be added to obtain good results.

That the solubility in acetic acid has got nothing to do with the p_H of the solution can be very well judged from the results. In the presence of mineral acid at a lower p_H value, the copper is completely precipitated, whereas in free acetic acid at a higher p_H value the copper is incompletely precipitated.

Further work in this line is in progress.

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